

Nitrophenols as Corrosion Inhibitors for Aluminium-Copper Alloy in Sodium Hydroxide

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Inhibition by nitrophenols of the corrosion of Al-4%Cu alloy (B26S) in solutions of sodium hydroxide has been studied. At constant alkali concentration, inhibitor efficiency increases with concentration of inhibitor, but at constant inhibitor concentration it decreases with increase in alkali concentration, there being even acceleration of attack at very low concentrations of nitrophenol. The inhibitive efficiency remains almost constant with temperature in the range 20-50° but increases with increase in the period of immersion. At an inhibitor concentration of 0.1-2.0% in 0.1 M NaOH, the efficiency increases in the order, *p*-nitrophenol < *m*-nitrophenol ≤ *o*-nitrophenol < phenol.

The inhibitors appear to function through adsorption following the Langmuir adsorption isotherm. Galvanostatic polarisation data and open circuit potentials suggest that all the four compounds are mixed type inhibitors.

ALUMINIUM-copper alloys are endowed with better mechanical properties¹ but have lower corrosion resistance. Pickling of aluminium surfaces² in 5-10% caustic soda solutions at 40-80° for about 2-5 min for degreasing prior to anodizing, or to give an attractive matt finish, is common practice^{3,4}. Mixtures of sodium carbonate and phosphate are also used^{5,6} for light cleaning. The action of alkaline cleaning solutions on aluminium is rapid and severe and therefore, it is desirable to inhibit the solution used for pickling. As pickling inhibitors should not have much effect on the pH of the alkaline solution, phenolic compounds with not too high a pK_a value have been investigated for the purpose. In earlier communications, the inhibition of corrosion of B26S aluminium (Al-4%Cu) in sodium hydroxide solutions by hydroxybenzenes⁷, cresols⁸, aminophenols⁹ and some substituted phenols^{10,11} were reported. In the present paper the action of nitrophenols as corrosion inhibitors for B26S aluminium in NaOH solutions is reported.

Experimental

Rectangular specimens of B26S aluminium (supplied by M/S Indian Aluminium Co. Ltd., Bombay), 5×4×0.09 cm with a small hole of ~2 mm diam near the upper edge of the specimen, were used for the determination of the corrosion rate. The percentage composition of the alloy was Cu, 3.88; Mn, 0.87; Fe, 0.43; Si, 0.59; Mg, < 0.32%; Al, the rest.

The specimens were polished according to the method described earlier^{10,11}, using tripoli composition followed by jeweller's rouge¹². The test specimens were exposed to caustic soda solutions

within the concentration range of 0.1-1.0 M, containing controlled additions (0.01 to 2.0%) of the inhibitor. One specimen only was suspended by a glass hook in each beaker containing 230 ml of the test solution at 30±0.5° (unless otherwise specified) and left exposed to the air. The specimens were cleaned after the tests in a dichromate-phosphoric acid mixture¹³. Duplicate experiments were performed in each case and the mean values of the weight losses are recorded.

For polarization measurements, metal coupons of circular design, 2.88 cm diam with a handle 3.2×0.48 cm, were used. The handle and the back of the coupon and of the auxiliary platinum electrode, were coated with a mixture of perspex and wax from chloroform solution leaving only a circular portion of apparent surface area 6.51 cm² exposed to the solution in an H-type cell with the Luggin capillary as near to the electrode surface as possible. The potential was measured with an accuracy of ±5 mV by a D. C. microvoltmeter using a saturated calomel electrode as reference. During galvanostatic polarization, the c.d. was varied in the range 1.54×10⁻⁵ to 1.54×10⁻⁸ A/cm².

Results and Discussion

The results are given in Figs. 1-4 and Tables 1-4. Inhibitor efficiency, *I*, is defined as:

$$I = \frac{W_u - W_i}{W_u} \times 100\%$$

where W_i = weight loss of metal in inhibited solution,

W_u = weight loss of metal in uninhibited solution.

In order to assess their effect as corrosion inhibitors, phenols and the three nitrophenols (*o*-, *m*- and

Fig. 1. Effect of concentration of NaOH on the inhibitive efficiency of phenol and nitrophenols for B26S aluminium (30°; 1hr).

Fig. 2A. Influence of immersion period on inhibitive efficiency of nitrophenols for B26S aluminium in 0.1M NaOH (30°; 1% inhibitor).

B. Effect of temperature on inhibitive efficiency of nitrophenols for B26S aluminium in 0.1M NaOH (1hr; 1% inhibitor).

▲—▲ Phenol, ●—● o-nitrophenol, x—x p-nitrophenol, △—△ m-nitrophenol.

Fig. 3. Arrhenius plots of log ρ (corrosion rate) vs 1/T

▲—▲ Phenol, x—x p-nitrophenol, ●—● o-nitrophenol, △—△ m-nitrophenol, ○—○ 0.1M NaOH

TABLE 1—pH VALUES OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF THE INHIBITOR AND OF INHIBITED 0.1 M NaOH

Inhibitor	pKa	pH of 1% aqueous inhibitor	pH of 0.1 M NaOH +0.1 M inhibitor	Wt. loss in 1% aq. soln. of inhibitor
Nil	—	—	12.8	—
Phenol	9.99*	7.0	11.4	Nil
o-nitrophenol	7.21*	5.2*	11.8	Nil
m-nitrophenol	8.39*	5.8	11.9	Nil
p-nitrophenol	7.15*	5.3	11.9	Nil

+ Data from Ref 14
* For saturated solution.

p-) were added in concentrations ranging from 0.01-2.0% to NaOH solutions of different molarities. The pH of 1.0% aqueous solutions of the inhibitors all lie in the range 5.2 (o-nitrophenol) to 7.0 (phenol) and the solutions are noncorrosive to aluminium (Table 1). The pH of the inhibited alkali (0.1M NaOH+0.1M inhibitor) solutions were found in the range 11.4 (phenol) to 11.9 (m- and p-nitrophenol), i.e. the inhibitors did not have much effect on the pH of the corrosive medium (Table 1).

As many of the results on inhibitor efficiency reported in the present work were obtained by experiments in 0.1M NaOH, it was considered necessary to find a reliable value of the mean weight loss in 0.1 M NaOH. For this purpose a large number (70) of replicate measurements were made and the mean value of the weight loss data was evaluated as 95.0 ± 1.0 mg. The standard deviation turned out to be 1.81. The coefficient of variation ($=s/m$) was found to be 0.019 while the accuracy of estimate for 95% probability limit was 95.0 ± 0.4446 .

Effect of inhibitor concentration :

The specimens exposed to corroding solutions containing 0.01-0.5% of the inhibitor were covered

Fig. 4. Galvanostatic polarization curves of B26S aluminium in 0.1M NaOH alone, and containing 0.1M inhibitor.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF INHIBITOR CONCENTRATION ON INHIBITIVE EFFICIENCY OF NITROPHENOLS FOR B26S ALUMINIUM IN 0.1 M NaOH

(Specimen size, 40 cm²; Temp. 30 ± 0.5°; Immersion period, 1 hr.)

Inhibitor	% inhibition at inhibitor concentration of						
	0.01 %	0.05%	0.1%	0.2%	0.5%	1.0%	2.0%
Nil	(95.0)*						
Phenol	10.6	11.4	13.6	18.8	31.5	83.3	100
<i>o</i> -nitrophenol	-16.8	-3.1	8.3	11.3	20.8	72.6	99.6
<i>m</i> -nitrophenol	-2.1	1.9	8.3	13.3	22.8	34.8	100
<i>p</i> -nitrophenol	-11.6	-3.1	1.8	6.2	13.6	55.3	98.7

* Weight loss in uninhibited 0.1 M NaOH

TABLE 3—INFLUENCE OF TEMPERATURE ON THE CORROSION OF B26S ALUMINIUM IN 0.1 M NaOH AND THE ENERGY OF ACTIVATION

(Surface area of specimen 40 sq. cm; Concentration of inhibitor, 1.0%; Immersion period: 1 hr.)

Inhibitor	Weight loss (mg) at °C				Energy of activation E kcal/mole
	20	30	40	50	
Nil	46.0	95.0	193.0	355.0	12.9
Phenol	7.1	15.9	31.8	64.7	13.7
<i>o</i> -nitrophenol	12.3	26.0	50.8	99.2	13.4
<i>m</i> -nitrophenol	16.2	34.8	71.0	130.1	13.0
<i>p</i> -nitrophenol	20.1	42.5	85.3	157.8	13.6

with a greyish film which could easily be removed with the cleaning mixture. At higher concentrations ($\geq 1.0\%$) of the inhibitor, no visible film formation was noticed but the specimens had a dull metallic appearance.

The effect of inhibitor concentration on inhibitive efficiency of phenol and the three nitrophenols is given in Table 2. In the case of phenol, the efficiency increased with inhibitor concentration from 10.6% with 0.01% phenol to ~100% with 2% of the inhibitor. However, with the three nitrophenols there was an acceleration of attack at concentrations $\leq 0.05\%$ but at higher concentrations ($\geq 0.1\%$), the efficiency increased with inhibi-

TABLE 4—TAFEL PARAMETERS AND INHIBITIVE EFFICIENCIES OF NITROPHENOLS FOR B26S ALUMINIUM IN 0.1 M NaOH

(Surface area of specimen: 6.51 sq. cm; Temp. 30 ± 0.5°; Inhibitor concentration 0.1 M)

Inhibitor	Open circuit potential (vs SCE) mV	Tafel slope mV/decade		Energy transfer coefficient (cathodic)	Corrosion current, A/cm ² , from extrapolation of		Inhibition efficiency (%) calculated from		Weight loss data
		Cathodic	Anodic		Cathodic Tafel line	Anodic Tafel line	Extrapolation of		
							Cathodic Tafel line	Anodic Tafel line	
Nil	-1470	35	98	1.71	2.82×10^{-4}	6.31×10^{-5}	-	-	-
Phenol	-1350	42	314	1.46	1.58×10^{-5}	2.11×10^{-5}	98.9	66.5	83.3
<i>o</i> -nitrophenol	-1040	67	428	0.90	1.58×10^{-5}	1.38×10^{-5}	94.4	78.1	96.4
<i>m</i> -nitrophenol	-760	217	83	0.28	3.47×10^{-5}	1.90×10^{-5}	87.7	89.8	95.7
<i>p</i> -nitrophenol	-890	25	179	2.40	4.57×10^{-5}	4.79×10^{-5}	83.8	24.1	95.7

tor concentration. The increase in corrosion with lower concentrations of nitrophenol may be attributed to the fact that the inhibitor depolarizes the electrode by removing hydrogen. At higher concentrations, the oxidizing action of the $-\text{NO}_2$ group probably helps in the repair and maintenance of the oxide film. It is also possible that a chemisorbed film of inhibitor molecules is formed on the metal surface. In the concentration range of 0.1-1.0% maximum protection was conferred by phenol and minimum by *p*-nitrophenol, the general order of efficiency in 0.1 *M* NaOH being *p*-nitrophenol < *m*-nitrophenol < *o*-nitrophenol < phenol. At 2.0% inhibitor concentration all the compounds conferred almost complete (~99-100%) protection to aluminium.

Effect of alkali concentration :

Fig. 1 shows the effect of concentration of NaOH on the inhibitive efficiency at three different concentrations of the inhibitors studied. It is evident from the results that the efficiency of all the four compounds decreases with increase in alkali concentration. In the case of nitrophenols, there is even an acceleration of attack in 0.5 and 1.0 *M* alkali, the effect being more pronounced the higher the inhibitor concentration. As stated earlier, the acceleration may be traced to the easy removal of hydrogen from the electrode surface due to the oxidizing action of the nitrophenol which thus acts as an anodic inhibitor. At lower concentrations (< 0.2 *M*) of alkali the general order of efficiency is *p*-nitrophenol < *o*-nitrophenol < *m*-nitrophenol < phenol.

In addition to the depolarizing action of the inhibitor the acceleration of attack at higher alkali concentrations may also be traced to incapability of the inhibitor to get chemisorbed under vigorous agitating conditions caused by the higher rate of hydrogen evolution.

Effect of immersion period :

Measurements of weight losses in 0.1 *M* NaOH containing 1.0% inhibitor for immersion periods of 15, 30, 45 and 60 min (Fig. 2A) showed that with phenol, the inhibitive efficiency decreased with an increase in the period of immersion. With all the three nitrophenols, however, the efficiency was found to increase with the period of immersion, the effect being minimum with *m*-nitrophenol (60.5→63.4%) and maximum with *o*-nitrophenol (46.1→72.6%). In general, the efficiency of the inhibitors increased in the order *p*-nitrophenol (55.3%) < *m*-nitrophenol < *o*-nitrophenol < phenol (83.3%).

Effect of temperature :

Fig. 2B shows the effect of temperature on the inhibitive efficiency of the four phenols for B26S aluminium in 0.1 *M* NaOH. From the weight loss data given in Table 3, it is evident that the corrosion rate in inhibited as well as uninhibited alkali is almost doubled for every 10° rise in temperature. Thus, even though the corrosion rate increases with temperature, the efficiency remains almost constant

in the range 20-50°. The average efficiency of inhibitors in the temperature range studied was *p*-nitrophenol (56%) < *m*-nitrophenol (64%) < *o*-nitrophenol (73%) < phenol (83%).

Plots of $\log \rho$ (corrosion rate) vs $1/T$ were linear (Fig. 3). This indicates that the corrosion process follows the Arrhenius equation,

$$\rho = A e^{-E/RT} \dots \quad (2)$$

[ρ =corrosion rate, A =constant depending on the reaction, E =energy of activation for the corrosion process, T =solution temperature (K)]

and that the values of the energy of activation can be calculated from the slope of the rectilinear plot. The E values for the corrosion process in 0.1 *M* NaOH (plain as well as inhibited) are given in Table 3. It may be generalised that the energy of activation for the corrosion process in uninhibited alkali or the alkali inhibited with nitrophenols has an almost constant value of 13.0 kcal mole⁻¹ for the temperature range 20-50°. The constant values of E are in agreement with a report¹⁵ that for the processes taking place in the presence of inhibitors which are similar in their structure and mechanism of action, the values of E are closely similar. Almost the same values of E in inhibited as well as uninhibited alkali indicate that the behaviour of the inhibitor resembles that of stable poisons in heterogeneous catalysis which, as Taylor¹⁶ has shown, do not affect the temperature coefficient of the reaction.

Polarization behaviour :

When immersed in 0.1 *M* NaOH, B26S aluminium developed a steady state potential of -1470 mV vs SCE. With 0.1 *M* inhibitor in 0.1 *M* NaOH the value of the open circuit potential increased (became less negative) in the case of all the four inhibitors (Table 4). The increase was maximum with *m*-nitrophenol and minimum with phenol. The shift of potential in a more noble direction indicates that the inhibitors have preponderant action on local anodes. However, there does not appear to be any correlation between inhibitor efficiency and the corrosion potential.

Anodic and cathodic galvanostatic polarization curves for B26S aluminium in 0.1 *M* NaOH, alone and containing 0.1 *M* concentration of the various inhibitors (i. e. the same number of molecules of each inhibitor) are shown in Fig 4. The curves show both anodic and cathodic polarization, anodic polarization being more pronounced than the cathodic. Thus, the open circuit potentials and polarization curves suggest that nitrophenols are mixed type inhibitors with predominant action on local anodes. When the inhibitive efficiencies were calculated from corrosion currents obtained by extrapolation of the anodic Tafel lines it was found that the efficiencies were lower than the values obtained from weight loss data. However, the efficiencies calculated from cathodic Tafel plots

almost agreed (within $\pm 15\%$) with those from weight loss data (Table 4).

Mechanism of inhibition :

Phenols are acids stronger than water and give phenolate ions when dissolved in caustic alkalis. Introduction of $-\text{NO}_2$ group in the benzene ring increases the acid character of the resulting nitrophenol as is evident from their lower pK_a values (Table 1). Thus nitrophenols can function as inhibitors in two ways :

- (i) by neutralizing the alkali to a certain extent, as is evident from slight decrease in pH values, and
- (ii) by being adsorbed on the metal surface.

The adsorption can take place through the negatively charged oxygen atom of the phenolate ion due to electrostatic attraction or the phenol molecule, because a lone pair of unshared electrons on the oxygen atom may be attached to the anodic points on the metal surface through the (negative) oxygen atom. The inhibitive effect due to adsorption becomes apparent from the fact that plots of log (inhibitive efficiency) vs log (inhibitor concentration) give straight lines for certain ranges of concentrations.

When the inhibitive efficiencies of the three nitrophenols are compared at 1.0% concentration in 0.1 M NaOH, the effect of the orientation of the $-\text{NO}_2$ group becomes evident. Thus *o*-nitrophenol shows more inhibition than *m*-nitrophenol followed by *p*-nitrophenol because *o*-nitrophenol with two adjacent functional groups might easily get attached to the metal surface. However, at lower inhibitor concentrations ($\leq 0.5\%$) *o*-nitrophenol must be functioning as an inhibitor more through electrostatic attraction due to preponderance of phenolate ions. Polarisation data also indicate that there is preponderant action on local anodes which further confirms that in alkaline solutions the negatively charged oxygen atom of the phenolate ion is more active.

Conclusions :

Additions of phenol and nitrophenols to NaOH solutions decrease the corrosion rate of B26S aluminium (Al-4%Cu alloy), the extent of inhibition being dependant on the concentration of alkali and of the inhibitor. Unlike phenol, the inhibitive efficiency of the nitrophenols increases with time, it

being more so in the case of *o*- and *p*-nitrophenol. The efficiency remains almost constant in the range 20-50°.

All the four compounds increase the open circuit potential to a more or less extent and appear to function with some preferential action on local anodes. The inhibitors appear to be directly attached to the metal surface either as phenolate ions by electrostatic attraction, or by chelate formation through the unshared pair of electrons on the nitrogen atom.

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